

Water polo game-related statistics in women's international championships as a function of final score differences

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Abstract

The aims of this study were: (i) to compare water polo game-related statistics by context (winning and losing teams) and final score differences (using three categories – “close” games, “unbalanced” games, and “very unbalanced” games); and (ii) to identify characteristics that mark the differences in performances for each of these three categories of final score differences. The game-related statistics of the 213 women's matches played in seven international championships were analysed. Differences between contexts (winning or losing teams) and final score differences (close, unbalanced, and very unbalanced games) were determined using the chi-squared statistic, also calculating the effect sizes of the differences. A discriminant analysis was then performed applying the sample-splitting method according to context in each final score. It was found that the game-related statistics differentiate the winning from the losing teams in each final score group, with one variable (penalty goals) differentiating winners from losers in close games, 12 in unbalanced games, and 13 (both offensive and defensive variables) in very unbalanced games. In all three types of game, the game-related statistics were shown to discriminate performance (82% or more), with three variables being discriminatory by context (winning or losing teams): goals, offensive fouls, and goalkeeper-blocked shots.

Keywords: Notational analysis, performance, discriminant analysis, match outcome.

1. Introduction

Water polo is a popular Olympic sport. In Europe for example, there are more than 23 associations affiliated with the International Swimming Federation (FINA). It is also undergoing rapid growth in the United States and Australia (Webster et al., 2009). Water polo is the second Olympic aquatic sport in number of research studies (Escalante and Saavedra, 2012). In the women's category, the support of FINA and the International Olympic Committee (IOC) helped water polo become a demonstration sport at the 1996 Atlanta Olympics. It was officially included as an Olympic sport in the 2000 Sydney Olympics. The rise of the sport in recent years has led to various studies being conducted to analyse the factors that contribute to success in women's water polo. The approaches taken have been physiological (Lupo et al., 2015), kinanthropometric (Alcaraz et al., 2011), and functional (McCluskey et al., 2010), inter alia. An interesting recent development in studies of the women's game has been the application of the technique known as "notational analysis" (Enomoto et al., 2004; Takagi et al., 2005; Argudo et al., 2007). This quantifies the technical/tactical playing aspects of a game through game-related statistics based mainly on frequencies and effectiveness percentages (Lozovina et al., 2004). In this sense, the variables found to discriminate between the winning and losing teams are shots and successful 5-m shots (Escalante et al., 2011). Other studies have confirmed the particular relevance of the position of goalkeeper (Saavedra et al., 2014). Thus, the goalkeeper-blocked shots variable is crucial in all phases of an international championship (preliminary, classification, and semi-final/bronze-medal/gold-medal) (Escalante et al., 2012). This last study also found that the variable which differentiates winning from losing teams is shooting effectiveness (goals), a finding that was consistent with those of a similar work that analysed several official matches of the 2008 National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) Championship (Lupo et al., 2011). This same study (Lupo et al., 2011) finds that, in an even play phase, the actions of the winning teams are quicker and more focused on scoring a direct goal or provoking an exclusion, and the winning teams make more shots from within the 5-m zone; in counterattack, their defence is more aggressive, and is followed by more direct counter movements seeking a shot without opposition.

Some studies examining the specific margin of victory have been carried out for several sports, including basketball (Sampaio & Janeira, 2003) and rugby (Vaz et al., 2010). In general, these studies group games into three categories: (i) close games, when the goal difference is small; (ii) unbalanced games when the goal difference is not large; and (iii) unbalanced games when the goal difference is large (Csataljay et al., 2009). They have shown that there are just a few technical/tactical actions that distinguish winners from losers in close games (Csataljay et al., 2009), but many in unbalanced games (Drikos & Vagenas, 2011). Despite the current proliferation of studies on the technical/tactical variables in women's water polo, only one (Lupo et al., 2014) has examined how to differentiate and discriminate between winners and losers in terms of the specific margin of victory (goal difference in the final score). That study's analysis was restricted to certain actions of the game (even, counterattack, power play, transition). Thus, the objectives of this present study were: (i) to compare water polo game-related statistics by context (winning and losing teams) and final score differences (also using three categories – “close” games, “unbalanced” games, and “very unbalanced” games – that were determined objectively as the result of a *k*-means cluster analysis); and (ii) to identify characteristics that mark the differences in performances for each of these three categories of final score differences.

2. Methods

2.1. Subjects

We analysed the results and game-related statistics of 213 women's matches played in 7 International Championships (12th FINA World Championships 2007, Melbourne, Australia; 13th FINA World Championships 2009, Rome, Italy; 28th European Water Polo Championships 2008, Málaga, Spain; 29th European Water Polo LEN Championships 2010, Zagreb, Croatia; 14th FINA World Championships 2011, Shanghai, China; 30th European Water Polo LEN Championships 2012, Eindhoven, Netherlands; and 30th Olympic Games 2012, London, United Kingdom).

2.2. Procedures

The official box scores provide information on the game statistics to analyse both for each player individually and for the team collectively. In particular, the data were retrieved from the box scores on the official OMEGA® Timing Website of (<http://www.omegatiming.com/>). The data were retrieved by one of the authors (AGH), and entered manually into an Excel file. They were then subjected to a random check by another of the authors (JMS) in order to detect possible errors. The analysis of public data taken from Websites is habitual in the field of water polo in particular (Escalante et al., 2011, 2012, 2013), and of water sports in general (Saavedra et al., 2012; Garcia-Hermoso et al., 2013, Saavedra et al. 2014).

The game-related statistics considered were: goals (percentage of converted shots relative to the number of shots made); even goals (percentage of converted shots in a situation of numerical equality relative to the number of shots made in this situation); centre goals (percentage of converted shots at the centre point of the mid-court line after each goal relative to the number of shots made); power play goals (percentage of shots converted in a situation of numerical superiority relative to the number of shots made in this situation); 5-m goals (percentage of shots converted at a distance of 5 metres relative to the number of shots made from that distance); penalty goals (percentage of penalties converted relative to the number of penalties taken); counterattacks (percentage of shots converted in a situation of counter-attack – rapid switch from defence to attack without allowing the opposing team time to get back into position – relative to the number of shots made in this situation); assists (number of passes from one offensive player to another leading directly to a goal score); offensive fouls (number of losses of the ball due to committing a foul); steals (number of turnovers in favour of the defence due to actions of anticipation and snatching the ball); blocked shots (shots stopped or diverted by the defenders); sprints (number of sprints won – possession of the first ball in each quarter – divided by four, i.e., by the number of sprints per game); timeouts (number of timeouts used throughout the game); exclusions (number of players expelled definitively from the match); goalkeeper-blocked shots (percentage of shots stopped relative to the number of shots made by the attackers); goalkeeper-blocked even shots (percentage of shots stopped in a situation of numerical equality relative to the number of shots made in this situation); goalkeeper-blocked centre shots (percentage of shots stopped made from the centre point of the mid-court line after each goal relative to the number of shots made in this situation); goalkeeper-blocked power play shots (percentage of shots stopped in a situation of numerical inferiority relative to the number of shots made by the attackers in this situation); goalkeeper-blocked 5-m shots (percentage of shots stopped relative to the number of shots made by the attackers at a

distance greater than 5 metres); goalkeeper-blocked penalty shots (percentage of penalties stopped relative to the number of penalties taken by the attackers); goalkeeper-blocked counterattacks (percentage of shots stopped in a situation of counterattack relative to the number of shots made by the attackers in this situation); possessions (a team's total number of possessions of the ball in a game); and possession time (a team's minutes of possession of the ball in a game). These game-related statistics are already of general use among water polo coaches and technicians, and are those that have been used in earlier studies (Escalante et al., 2011, 2012, 2013; Lupo et al., 2012; Lupo et al., 2014).

2.3. Statistical analysis

A cluster analysis was conducted to establish three different groups according to final score differences. Three groups were defined: close games, (final score differences of between 1 and 3 goals), unbalanced games (final score differences of between 4 and 11 goals), and very unbalanced games (final score differences of 12 goals or more). The technique used was the *k*-means clustering algorithm. This uses prototypes (centroids) to represent clusters by optimizing the squared error function (Hartigan & Wong, 1979). The results of this analysis classified 53.5% of the games as close, 34.7% as unbalanced, and 11.8% as very unbalanced games. Other studies have used a similar nomenclature (Lupo et al., 2012, 2014). In regards to the type of championship, in European Championships, the results of the analysis classified 66.7% of the games as close, 21.1% as unbalanced, and 12.3% as very unbalanced; in World Championships, 45.6% of the games were classified as close, 41.4% as unbalanced, and 13.2% as very unbalanced. Finally, in the Olympic Games, 70.0% of the games were classified as close and 30.0% as unbalanced. Basic statistical descriptors (mean and standard deviation) were calculated by context (winning and losing teams) and by final score difference (close games, unbalanced games, and very unbalanced games). The significance of the descriptors distinguishing between winning and losing teams was determined by means of a chi-squared test, the recommended technique when the descriptors are discrete frequency response variables (Nevill et al., 1999; Nevill et al., 2002). The effect sizes of the differences were calculated (Cohen, 1988). Pearson's simple correlation coefficient was used to determine correlations between the variables studied. The values of this statistic were interpreted in terms of size following recommendations in the literature (Hopkins et al., 2009): >0.1 small, >0.3 moderate, >0.5 large, >0.7 very large, and >0.9 nearly perfect. The predictor variables influencing the final performance in the games (winning teams) were determined by means of a discriminant analysis using the sample-splitting method according to context (winning and losing teams) and final score (close games, unbalanced games, and very unbalanced games). The criterion used to determine whether or not a variable was discriminatory was Wilks's lambda (λ), which measures the deviations within each group with respect to the total deviations. We also calculated the canonical correlation indices (deviations of the between-group discriminant scores relative to the total deviations) and the percentage of correctly classified matches by final goal difference (close games, unbalanced games, and very unbalanced games). This methodological approach has been used in studies of other aquatic disciplines, including swimming (Saavedra et al., 2010). A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant. The statistical analysis was performed with the software package SPSS version 19.0.

3. Results

Table 1 presents the basic descriptors of the variables by match outcome (winning / losing teams) in each final score difference category. In the close games only a single variable (penalty goals) differentiates between winning and losing teams. In the unbalanced and very unbalanced games, there are eight common differentiating variables: even goals, centre goals, counterattacks, assists, blocked shots, sprints, timeouts, and goalkeeper-blocked 5-m shots.

Table 2 gives the values of Pearson's simple correlation coefficient between the variables studied. The relationships between most pairs of variables is small. The exceptions are: (i) goals and even goals, power play goals, assists ($r > 0.5$, large); (ii) goalkeeper-blocked shots and goalkeeper-blocked even shots ($r > 0.5$, large); (iii) sprints and goals, assists ($r < 0.3$, moderate); (iv) even goals and assists ($r < 0.3$, moderate); and (v) goalkeeper-blocked shots and goalkeeper-blocked power play shots ($r < 0.3$, moderate).

Table 3 presents the results of the discriminant analysis for each final score difference category. The predictive models correctly classified 82.4% of the close games using five variables (goals, offensive fouls, steals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, possession time), 100% of the unbalanced games using seven variables (goals, centre goals, 5-m goals, counterattacks, offensive fouls, goalkeeper-blocked shots, possessions), and 100% of the very unbalanced games using five variables (goals, offensive fouls, steals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, 5-m goals).

Table 1. Basic descriptors (mean and standard deviation), chi-squared statistic, *p*-value, and the effect sizes of the differences (Cohen's *d*) for each variable according to the context in each type of match.

Variable	Close (n=114)					Unbalanced (n=74)					Very unbalanced (n=25)				
	Winners M ± SD	Losers M ± SD	X ²	p	E.S.	Winners M ± SD	Losers M ± SD	X ²	p	E.S.	Winners M ± SD	Losers M ± SD	X ²	p	E.S.
Goals (%) ^a	57.8±8.60	37.3±9.96	153.3	0.147	2.21	45.0±10.0	24.6±8.62	132.0	0.051	2.18	57.8±8.58	18.6±8.14	50.0	0.247	4.69
Even goals (%) ^a	50.7±14.5	30.2±17.8	67.5	0.293	1.26	38.4±19.6	19.9±17.5	78.4	0.026	1.00	50.7±14.5	16.4±19.7	47.0	0.033	1.98
Centre goals (%) ^a	49.2±28.8	41.9±34.5	26.7	0.113	0.23	50.4±31.6	30.9±35.4	41.1	0.012	0.58	49.2±28.8	8.80±27.7	33.8	0.006	1.43
Power play goals (%) ^a	75.5±18.7	55.7±24.7	49.4	0.172	0.90	62.0±27.4	38.7±25.1	57.5	0.004	0.89	75.5±18.7	39.2±30.4	29.6	0.100	1.44
5-m goals (%) ^a	42.4±24.7	24.8±17.3	63.4	0.427	0.82	29.5±22.2	12.0±13.3	59.1	0.153	0.96	42.4±24.7	7.27±8.49	35.2	0.019	1.90
Penalty goals (%) ^a	66.0±45.0	49.7±49.3	15.5	0.030	0.35	50.5±47.3	41.9±49.3	7.62	0.106	0.18	66.0±45.0	46.0±47.7	2.32	0.314	0.43
Counterattacks (%) ^a	64.6±42.0	36.7±45.1	8.58	0.572	0.64	55.5±43.9	15.3±33.4	38.6	<0.001	1.03	64.6±41.8	8.33±28.2	22.5	0.002	1.58
Assists (n)	7.84±5.05	5.04±2.92	14.6	0.330	0.68	6.66±3.18	3.38±2.46	43.7	<0.001	1.15	7.84±5.05	1.20±1.04	37.8	<0.001	1.82
Offensive fouls (n)	11.5±3.55	14.0±3.73	14.0	0.826	-0.69	13.7±3.48	15.5±4.51	16.2	0.643	-0.46	11.5±3.55	23.8±4.46	44.3	0.005	-3.03
Steals (n)	13.0±4.53	6.99±3.15	12.5	0.563	1.54	7.89±3.63	6.40±2.69	24.2	0.084	0.46	13.0±4.53	5.24±2.55	33.5	0.004	2.11
Blocked shots (n)	2.12±1.54	2.77±1.82	11.7	0.164	-0.39	2.55±1.82	1.42±1.38	21.2	0.006	0.70	2.12±1.54	0.84±0.85	13.1	0.023	1.03
Sprints (%) ^b	74.2±21.5	52.2±28.2	2.99	0.885	0.88	70.3±30.2	29.7±30.2	42.0	<0.001	1.35	74.1±21.5	25.0±22.1	28.9	<0.001	2.25
Timeouts (n)	0.68±0.75	1.51±0.68	16.0	0.101	-1.16	1.26±0.72	1.47±0.58	6.17	0.046	-0.33	0.68±0.75	1.48±0.51	16.7	<0.001	-1.25
Exclusions (n)	0.40±0.71	1.01±1.19	7.27	0.203	-0.62	0.66±1.00	0.70±0.77	5.50	0.240	-0.05	0.40±0.71	0.60±0.71	2.73	0.255	-0.28
G.B. shots (%) ^c	65.9±14.4	52.8±10.8	127.8	0.253	1.02	59.9±11.4	38.3±12.4	130.4	0.016	1.81	65.9±14.4	26.5±8.91	48.0	0.243	3.29
G.B. even shots (%) ^c	62.4±38.2	57.2±28.7	52.4	0.153	0.15	66.3±27.3	46.7±24.5	47.8	0.090	0.75	62.4±38.2	31.0±16.7	37.2	0.042	1.07
G.B. centre shots (%) ^c	35.0±47.9	44.0±42.3	23.0	0.114	-0.20	35.0±38.5	34.8±31.1	30.5	0.062	0.01	35.0±47.9	32.3±30.0	26.1	0.025	0.07
G.B. power play s. (%) ^c	34.4±34.2	33.7±28.3	39.2	0.078	0.02	46.7±30.3	24.2±28.0	40.5	0.013	0.77	34.4±34.2	13.4±15.5	20.0	0.171	0.79
G.B. 5-m shots (%) ^c	84.5±18.5	69.2±27.2	34.0	0.514	0.66	75.2±26.5	43.9±30.6	27.3	0.004	1.09	84.5±18.5	33.1±25.0	38.8	0.005	2.34
G.B. penalty shots (%) ^c	18.0±35.0	14.1±29.8	10.4	0.651	0.12	5.79±21.9	9.39±25.3	4.44	0.329	-0.15	18.0±35.0	10.0±25.0	1.10	0.577	0.26
G.B. counterattacks (%) ^c	8.33±28.2	15.0±33.2	10.3	0.243	-0.22	16.5±35.0	12.9±3.85	12.2	0.200	0.12	8.33±28.2	15.2±29.7	8.32	0.305	-0.24
Possessions (n)	47.6±4.28	41.8±4.16	18.8	0.596	1.37	42.4±4.11	41.3±3.85	31.5	0.036	0.28	47.6±4.28	45.5±3.70	16.7	0.335	0.51
Possession time (min)	14.3±1.00	16.4±1.43	149.3	0.677	-1.69	15.6±1.21	16.2±1.27	96.0	0.423	-0.46	14.3±1.00	17.6±1.08	46.0	0.389	-3.15

^a= number of shots converted / number of shots. ^b= number of sprints won / number of sprints swum. ^c = number of shots saved / number of shots. G.B.= goalkeeper-blocked , s.=shot. E.S.= effect size.

Table 2. Pearson's simple correlation coefficient between all the possible pairs of the variables studied.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Goals (1)	-																				
Even goals (2)	.596	-																			
Centre goals (3)	.341	.104	-																		
Power play goals (4)	.501	.155	.147	-																	
5-m goals (5)	.541	.175	.038	.168	-																
Penalty goals (6)	.208	.006	-.031	.059	.008	-															
Counterattacks (7)	.357	.190	.097	.047	.161	.096	-														
Assists (8)	.521	.375	.253	.244	.216	.062	.295	-													
Offensive fouls (9)	-.124	-.109	-.112	-.063	-.085	-.003	-.115	-.231	-												
Steals (10)	.263	.144	.101	.153	.188	-.055	.209	.242	-.144	-											
Blocked shots (11)	.179	.088	.079	.027	.122	.122	.100	.123	-.076	-.137	-										
Sprints (12)	.343	.225	.083	.097	.227	.032	.165	.340	.176	.184	-.157	-									
Timeouts (13)	-.217	-.191	-.146	-.102	-.137	.010	-.129	-.110	.043	-.199	.017	-.065	-								
Exclusions (14)	.114	.072	.074	.053	.078	.064	-.058	.114	-.028	-.061	.031	-.086	.127	-							
G.B. shots (15)	.315	.169	.151	.176	.223	.089	.147	.171	.147	.085	.160	.281	-.154	-.100	-						
G.B. even shots (16)	.101	.080	.074	.090	.042	-.011	.037	.052	-.087	.013	.026	.161	-.077	-.134	.521	-					
G.B. centre shots (17)	-.041	.010	.090	-.034	-.005	-.006	.022	.026	.077	.015	.005	-.067	.066	.023	.215	.072	-				
G.B. power play s. (18)	.141	.077	.052	.066	.080	.016	.011	.146	-.046	.017	.023	.071	-.034	.065	.427	.110	.043	-			
G.B. 5-m shots (19)	.254	.125	.124	.146	.127	.124	.159	.188	-.139	.035	.126	.232	-.175	-.036	.552	.114	-.022	.098	-		
G.B. penalty shots (20)	.001	.016	-.043	.023	-.027	.094	-.063	.008	-.006	.061	-.032	.051	-.026	.140	.124	.027	-.009	.035	.057	-	
G.B. counterattacks (21)	.045	-.028	-.003	.084	.028	.120	.070	.096	.070	.027	.039	-.039	.077	-.011	.061	-.038	.084	-.069	.020	.001	-

Text in bold= p<0.05; G.B.= goalkeeper-blocked , s.=shot.

Table 3. Discriminant analysis models by type of match, giving the percentage correctly classified, Wilks's λ , canonical correlation index, and variables included in the model by order of selection.

Phase	Close (n=114)	Unbalanced (n=74)	Very unbalanced (n=25)
Percentage correctly classified	82.4	100.0	100.0
Wilks's lambda	0.567	0.142	0.052
Canonical correlation index	0.658	0.926	0.974
Variables selected	Goals, offensive fouls, steals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, possession time	Goals, centre goals, 5-m goals, counterattacks, offensive fouls, goalkeeper-blocked shots, possessions	Goals, offensive fouls, steals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, 5-m goals

4. Discussion

In the present study, we have analysed the women's game variables that differentiate and discriminate the winning from the losing teams as a function of the specific margin of victory. This type of study allows specific criteria to be established to guide coaches in forming their strategies according to the a priori likely final goal margin (Drikos & Vagenas, 2011; Lupo et al., 2012, 2014). It has shown that more than half of the games (53.5%) in women's international water polo championships are decided with very narrow goal differences (close games, 1-3 goals difference), while 34.7% are unbalanced games (4-11 goals difference), and only 11.8% very unbalanced (12 goals or more difference). The present results therefore provide a coach with the opportunity to approach upcoming games in accordance with their team's real chances of winning. Essentially, three different situations may present themselves in which this information may be particularly useful: (i) being in a position where winning is a clear possibility (close games); (ii) having a somewhat distant chance of winning (unbalanced games), in which case the objective would be to focus on reducing the gap on the scoreboard; and (iii) having really no chance of winning (very unbalanced games), in which case the match strategy can serve to improve some particular technical/tactical aspect of the team at the same time as trying to keep alive the remote chance of victory and the esteem of the players in having performed their best.

4.1. Differences by context (winning/losing teams)

The variables that differentiate winning and losing teams vary in number depending on the type of game (close, unbalanced, or very unbalanced). While in close games there was just a single differentiating variable (penalty goals), in the unbalanced and very unbalanced games the number of differentiating variables increased considerably (to 12 and 13, respectively). Overall therefore, the study has shown that there are fewer differentiating variables between teams when the outcome of the game is tighter. This is coherent with previous studies that have analysed the specific margin of victory depending on the game situation (Lupo et al., 2014) and the successive phases of international women's championships (Escalante et al., 2012). In particular, as the phase of a championship becomes more demanding and competitive, fewer technical/tactical variables differentiate the winners from the losers (Takagi et al., 2005).

The only variable differentiating between teams in close games was that of the penalty goals. No literature study of women's water polo has described this variable as differentiating between winning and losing teams (Escalante et al., 2011; Vila et al., 2011). Neither was any difference between winning and losing teams found in another recent study of women's water polo which included an analysis of the success frequency of penalty goals in a close game (Lupo et al., 2014). This divergence in results may reflect differences in the quality of the competitions analysed. In unbalanced games and in even game situations, however, the winning teams achieved a higher proportion of successful penalty goals. Another study found winning teams to have a greater proportion of exclusions and penalty goals in even play situations (Lupo et al., 2011).

Regarding the unbalanced and very unbalanced games, the 12 and 13 technical/tactical variables that differentiate the winning from the losing teams included 8 that were common to both. These were even goals, centre goals, counterattacks, assists, goalkeeper-blocked shots, goalkeeper-blocked 5-m shots, sprints, and timeouts. The present findings are coherent with those obtained for the preliminary phase of women's

international water polo championships (Escalante et al., 2012). This suggests that players' shooting efficiency (even goals and centre goals) and the goalkeeper's actions (goalkeeper-blocked shots and goalkeeper-blocked 5-m shots) are essential elements for success in unbalanced and very unbalanced games. This aspect is accentuated in situations of numerical equality (Argudo et al., 2010). Assists add to the effectiveness of goal actions since they reflect the team's ability to produce disequilibrating actions that lead directly to a goal when the teams are in numerical equality. This is also consistent with other studies that have concluded that winning teams make more counterattacks (Takagi et al., 2005; Lupo et al., 2011) and blocked shots (Takagi et al., 2005). Similarly, winning teams produce a higher proportion of specific action outcome goals (i.e., even shots, centre shots, 5-m shots) in different game situations (Lupo et al., 2014).

The greater number of sprints won by winning teams agrees with the observations reported in a recent study of the qualifying and preliminary phases of women's water polo (Escalante et al., 2012). In this line, it has already been noted how winning the first possession influences the final result, suggesting that first possession could be of particular importance when there is a clear difference in level between the teams (Argudo et al., 2011). This variable would clearly be conditioned by greater fitness (Tan et al., 2010) and technique of the winning teams' players (Aleksandrović et al., 2007). Finally, losing teams took more timeouts. This could be indicative either of the need to adjust tactical aspects to try to reduce the differences or of the players having less capacity to autonomously resolve game situations. Indeed, such autonomy has taken on particular importance with the reduction of possession time from 35 to 30 seconds since coaches are now using more defensive pressure (Baramenti & Platanou, 2010). This forces players to be better prepared physically, and the attackers to be faster in their decision-making so as to be able to execute their offensive actions successfully (Royal et al., 2006).

4.2. Discriminatory power

The discriminatory power analysis showed that three variables (goals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, and offensive fouls) could correctly classify more than 82% of the teams in the three types of game (close, 82%; unbalanced, 100%; very unbalanced, 100%). These results reflect the importance of creating offensive situations that allow: (i) offensive actions to be finalized with effective shots (goals); (ii) opposing shots to be stopped (goalkeeper-blocked shots) by the goalkeeper's action itself, by selecting defensive systems that do not permit the opponent to get into comfortable shooting situations, or by a combination of the two; and (iii) to achieve the sufficient offensive intensity to unbalance the defence without committing a foul (offensive fouls). These findings are consistent with studies of the Beijing Olympic Games (Escalante et al., 2011) and of different phases (preliminary, qualifying, and final) of international championships (Escalante et al., 2012).

In the close games, as well as the aforementioned variables, steals and possession time are also predictive of the winning teams. Steals are the result of appropriate defensive strategies that cause the attacking team to lose possession, thus not only preventing the offensive action ending in a shot but also making a counterattack possible. In men's water polo, the possession time variable also appears to be discriminatory (Escalante et al., 2013), although that study analysed games in which one would expect a priori the levels of the teams to be more disparate (preliminary and classificatory phases of the competitions). In the unbalanced games, besides the variables common to the two types

of game, those corresponding to centre goals, 5-m goals, counterattacks, and possessions correctly classified 100% of the teams. The effectiveness of shots on goal from the five-metre line (5-m goals) and from the centre position (centre goals) are variables that have been found to successfully qualify teams (winner/loser) in the three phases of competitions (Escalante et al., 2012). Winning teams have more ball possessions and counterattacks. In this regard, a greater number of counterattacks (Takagi et al., 2005; Madera et al., 2007; Lupo et al., 2011; Escalante et al., 2012, 2013) and their greater efficacy (Argudo et al., 2007) differentiate winning from losing teams. Finally, in the very unbalanced games, steals and 5-m goals are added to the common variables to correctly classify 100% of the women's water polo teams.

4.3. Limitations

The present study has certain limitations. First, grouping the teams based only on the final game outcome masks the real differences that occur in each quarter. In this sense, one might analyse game statistics based either on the goal difference in each quarter or on the evolution of the score. Second, the discriminant analysis applied post hoc prediction. In interpreting the results, one must bear in mind that this type of prediction usually gives better values for the classification than a priori prediction. And third, a few of the variables studied are related, so that the discriminant analysis may be slightly overestimated.

5. Conclusions

The results have shown that fewer game-related statistics differentiate between winning and losing teams as the games are resolved with smaller differences (close games). In the discriminant analysis, there were three variables (goals, goalkeeper-blocked shots, and offensive fouls) which correctly classified more than 82% of the teams in the three types of game (close, 82%; unbalanced, 100%; very unbalanced, 100%). These findings may help to orient coaches both in the preparation of a game in accordance with the possible differences between the teams and during the course of the game. However, it is necessary to continue work with this type of analysis, including other aspects such as the frequency in close games of both shots on goal and blocks so as to establish their relevance for the final outcome.

The present findings allow coaches and researchers to see how water polo game-related statistics in international competitions differ by context (winning and losing teams) and final score differences (close games, unbalanced games, and very unbalanced games). For practical purposes, there are three technical/tactical aspects that are fundamental for an effective approach to the various demands of competition: (i) the efficacy of shots on goal (goals); (ii) the efficacy of the goalkeeper's prevention of opponents scoring (goalkeeper-blocked shots); and (iii) control of intensity in attack so as to avoid committing offensive fouls (offensive fouls).

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